

The European Health Data Space needs to be relevant for paediatric data to support future medicines development for children- a conect4children viewpoint

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Abstract

The Innovative Medicines Initiative2 (IMI2)-funded conect4children (c4c) project was established to overcome the many barriers and challenges to the planning and delivery of effective and efficient paediatric clinical trials. c4c has been instrumental in bringing stakeholders together to foster collaborations and to develop resources with the aim of improving the standardization and harmonization of the data collected in paediatric clinical trials. It is also exploring the implications on the collection of paediatric data in healthcare, for primary use, given its potential importance for reuse in clinical research.

In April 2024, Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) approved the creation of the European Health Data Space (EHDS). The EHDS aims to improve citizens' access to and control over their electronic health data for primary (healthcare) and secondary (clinical research) uses. Anticipating the endorsement of the EHDS Regulation, c4c held a workshop in February 2024 to explore the potential impact of this legislation on paediatric clinical trials. The workshop highlighted that the unique challenges of paediatric data had not been formally considered in the design of the EHDS, particularly when it comes to the provisions in it for the primary use of health data.

This paper highlights the collaborations and resources developed and fostered by c4c that aim to address the gaps in paediatric data standards and increase awareness of the need for interoperability. These standards also have a role to improve the care of children as they transition into adulthood as they provide standardized data that can support continuity of care. The collaborations and resources developed over the life of the c4c project will now also play an important role in pushing the paediatric agenda within the EHDS to ensure it does not miss a vital opportunity to accelerate paediatric research and, by extension, rare disease research.

Introduction

The Innovative Medicines Initiative2 (IMI2)-funded conect4children (c4c)¹ is a private-public project, established to overcome the many barriers to the planning and delivery of effective and efficient paediatric clinical trials. Despite scientific advances, safety and efficacy data on the use of medicines in children is scarce leading to widespread off-label usage of medicines. There is a growing understanding of the need to reuse data from paediatric clinical trials in other trials and to reuse routinely collected (real world) paediatric data for observational research and for the design of future trials.

Paediatric data standards play an important role in facilitating the reuse of data in healthcare, policy making, research, and innovation; however, these standards often lack paediatric specificity as their development has historically focussed on adults and do not take into consideration the unique challenges described below, associated with paediatric data².

- Normal ranges for lab tests change as children age.
- Children can be affected by diseases that do not affect adults and there is a big gap in data standards for representing these conditions.
- Age is usually captured in terms of years or years and months. For some paediatric populations age needs to be captured in days, months or even hours.
- There can be complexity in capturing critical data about neonates as it includes data about two subjects - the baby and the mother. It also includes data items about birth and pregnancy.
- Children cannot consent to the use of their data, and ages and regulations concerning assent and consent differ across EU countries.
- General challenges around the scarcity of data and problems with data silos in small paediatric (and rare disease) populations.

The c4c data coordinating centre and data quality standards work package has led on the development of several collaborations and resources to address these challenges and promote the standardization and harmonization of paediatric clinical trial data. The collaborations and resources described below aim to increase data interoperability and therefore make paediatric data more reuse ready.

Background

Collaboration with CDISC

Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC)³ standards are required for submissions to the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and Japan's Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA), recommended by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the China National Medical Products Administration (NMPA) and adopted by the world's leading research organizations.

c4c collaborated with CDISC to develop the Pediatrics User Guide (PUG)⁴. A team consisting of CDISC standards experts, paediatric clinical research experts from CDISC member organizations and paediatric subject matter experts from the c4c consortium followed the CDISC standards

¹ <https://conect4children.org/>

² <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/hpm.3592>

³ <https://www.cdisc.org/>

⁴ <https://www.cdisc.org/standards/therapeutic-areas/pediatrics>

development process to identify and prioritize 90 data element concepts unique to paediatric clinical research for representation in the PUG. The PUG was published in February 2023 and is freely available as a therapeutic area standard on the CDISC website⁵.

The CDISC Pediatric User Network (CPUN)⁶ was formed in late 2023 to continue the work to identify and address gaps in CDISC standards with regards to paediatrics. Work is also underway to develop a CDISC paediatric training module which will be available by late 2024.

Collaboration with IMI FAIRPlus

c4c collaborated with IMI FAIRPlus⁷ to develop a metadata schema to make the metadata collected about paediatric clinical trials more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)⁸. The process for developing the metadata schema is described in the recipe 'A metadata profile for clinical trial protocols'⁹ in the online FAIR Cookbook. This work aims to reduce siloed data and provide the foundations for data sharing.

Workshop on Increasing the Harmonization and Standardization of Disease-Specific Paediatric Trial Data

In May 2022, c4c hosted a workshop 'Increasing the Harmonization and Standardization of Disease-Specific Paediatric Trial Data'¹⁰ in Rome. The workshop brought together representatives from health and research related organizations, initiatives and projects working on different aspects of data harmonization, standardization, and interoperability.

The workshop provided a forum to learn about and discuss resources, initiatives and infrastructures developed within and outside c4c with the potential to harmonize and standardize paediatric clinical trial data and increase the utility and reusability of such data. The workshop also considered case studies for what researchers want to do with pooled paediatric data to clarify what kind of data needs to be accessible.

One of the actions from the workshop was the formation of the Global Paediatric Data Forum (GLOPAD). The GLOPAD meets quarterly online to continue the collaboration that came out of the workshop and to continue to push the paediatric agenda world-wide.

Workshop on Engaging with the European Health Data Space: The Paediatric Perspective

A second workshop 'Workshop on Engaging with the European Health Data Space: The Paediatric Perspective'¹¹ was held in Amsterdam in February 2024 with the aim of gaining a better understanding of the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS)¹². The EHDS will allow citizens to securely access their primary health data (such as prescriptions, image reports, laboratory test results and hospital discharge summaries) electronically across different EU countries. It will also allow for secondary use health datasets to be shared securely for research purposes. The EHDS will

⁵ <https://www.cdisc.org/standards/therapeutic-areas>

⁶ <https://wiki.cdisc.org/display/PEDUN>

⁷ <https://fairplus-project.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁹ <https://w3id.org/faircookbook/FCB084>

¹⁰ <https://www.mdpi.com/2306-5729/9/4/55>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11191557>

¹² <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240304IPR18765/eu-health-data-space-to-support-patients-and-research>

also address important cross border healthcare implications by facilitating better data sharing across borders.¹³

The original European patient summary guidelines were published by the eHealth Network in 2011. This patient summary specification is part of a wider set of electronic health record information objects included in the European EHR exchange format (EEHRxF)¹⁴, the adoption of which is presently recommended but optional. The EHDS Regulation will mandate the adoption of this interoperability standard, which will be more precisely detailed through forthcoming implementation acts. However, in recent years there has been an international movement to promote a global patient summary, reflected in an existing ISO standard¹⁵ but more importantly an updated version that is close to final: the International Patient Summary (IPS). It is widely expected that the EEHRxF will migrate to incorporating the IPS.

Several studies^{16,17} have examined the core data element concepts that frequently occur as clinical trial eligibility criteria, across therapeutic areas, and the data element concepts that are valuable to screen before inviting a patient to participate in a clinical trial. There is substantial overlap between these core data elements and the IPS.

The xSHARE project¹⁸ seeks to bring these inventories of data elements together, in an activity being jointly led by CDISC and I~HD¹⁹. It is anticipated that the resulting combined specification, termed the IPS+R, will not be a substantial increase on the existing IPS. It will therefore be a feasible proposition to the European Commission (EC) and to European Member States to instead include this in the exchange format. Another new European Project, Xt-EHR²⁰ is charged with collecting inputs to inform the evolution of the exchange format, and xSHARE had the original intention to offer the IPS+R to Xt-EHR for consideration by the EC.

All of the prior work to develop the IPS and to develop the inventory of clinical trial data element concepts has focused on adults. c4c has developed a core data dictionary for data elements that are most relevant to paediatric clinical trials and these data element concepts have now become incorporated into the CDISC PUG described above.

The workshop brought together stakeholders from the projects and initiatives working on the development of the EHDS, together with stakeholders who generate and use paediatric data. The discussion highlighted that the unique needs of paediatric data had not yet been considered in the development of the EHDS.

As a direct result of the workshop, it is now proposed to combine efforts to generate a specification for the IPS+R that is suitable for adults and children. Since many rare diseases are diagnosed in childhood and subject to clinical research during childhood, this extended IPS+R is also likely to cover the common data element concepts relevant to the design and screening of patients for rare disease clinical trials. The combined IPS+R will help address the problem of both neglected populations falling further behind in medicines development.

¹³ [Questions and answers – EU Health: European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#)

¹⁴ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/electronic-health-records>

¹⁵ <https://international-patient-summary.net>

¹⁶ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36602707/>

¹⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1532046412001037>

¹⁸ <https://xshare-project.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.i-hd.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.xt-ehr.eu/>

Proposed solutions

The resources and collaborations that have been developed over the lifespan of c4c continue to be disseminated to promote an increased understanding of the importance of interoperability of paediatric clinical trial data.

- The ongoing collaboration with CDISC to develop the CPUN and training on implementing paediatric standards will help ensure the standardized collection, tabulation, and analysis of paediatric data for regulatory purposes.
- c4c are using the metadata schema developed in the collaboration with FAIRPlus to explore the creation of a FAIR Data point to make the metadata collected about c4c studies more FAIR.
- The GLOPAD will continue the collaborations that have developed during the lifespan of c4c and helps to ensure that the global paediatric agenda is central to discussions about data standardization and harmonization.
- c4c has been carrying out research into Real World Data (RWD) by exploring the interoperability between Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and clinical trial data.
- The collaboration with xSHARE to integrate paediatric data element concepts into the IPS+R will ensure that the unique needs of children are not missed in the development of the EHDS.
- A collaboration between c4c and the European Young Person's Advisory Group Network (eYPAGnet)²¹ is planned for late 2024/early 2025. Children and young people associated with the eYPAGnet will be asked a series of questions to gain a better understanding of their views and opinions on whether and how their data should be shared. They will also be asked if they are aware of the EHDS. The results of this collaboration will be disseminated to add the voice of children and young people to recommendations around the standardization and harmonization of paediatric data.

Conclusion

The scarcity of safety and efficacy data on the use of medicines in children and the growing understanding of the need to therefore reuse data from paediatric clinical trials highlights the need for increased standardization and harmonization of paediatric data by addressing the lack of paediatric specificity in the development of data standards.

The resources developed under the remit of the c4c project aim to address this issue and increase the pool of reuse-ready data. The collaborations described above will ensure that they continue to have an impact on the standardization and harmonization of paediatric clinical trial data beyond the life of the c4c project.

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²¹ <https://eypagnet.eu/>